

IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF ELASTOMER BASED FIBRE METAL LAMINATES

R. Das*, S. Rao, and R.J.T. Lin

Centre for Advanced Composite Materials, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand.

*Corresponding author (r.das@auckland.ac.nz)

Keywords: *FML, Composites, Impact, Modelling, Energy absorption, Elastomer.*

Abstract

Research has shown that fibre metal laminates (FMLs) are better than monolithic alloys in terms of corrosion resistance, fatigue load, high blast resistance and impact energy absorption. This study aims to explore the potential of manufacturing a new type of FML by introducing fibre reinforced thermoplastic elastomer (FRTPE) layers to replace conventional fibre reinforced thermoplastic polymer (FRTPP) layers within FMLs. With the well-known high damping capability of the elastomer, an FRTPE laminate is expected to have improved impact resistance and shock load absorption ability when compared with its FRTPP layered counterpart.

With aluminium sheet as the metal component, different types of FMLs were manufactured using thermoplastic polymers (TPP) and thermoplastic elastomers (TPE) as matrix to incorporate glass fibre reinforcement for FRTPP and FRTPE laminates. A finite element model was developed using ABAQUS to understand the impact behaviour of the proposed FRTPE FML system. The manufactured TPE and TPP based FMLs have been evaluated for their tensile and impact properties. Tensile testing showed that FRTPP based FMLs have higher strengths and moduli, whereas impact strength significantly improved for FRTPE based FMLs as demonstrated by energy absorption during drop weight tests.

1. Introduction

Fibre metal laminates (FMLs) are hybrid composite materials built up from interlacing layers of thin metals and fibre reinforced polymers (Fig. 1)[1]. They consist of thin, high strength aluminium alloy sheets alternately bonded to plies of fibre reinforced polymer (FRP). FMLs provide excellent mechanical properties resulting from the combination of the best properties of both materials. FMLs offer several advantages compared to

conventional metal alloys, such as superior fatigue behaviour, excellent damage tolerance properties, high resistance to crack propagation and corrosion, and labour savings due to less number of parts required for fabrication, which make them the ideal materials for aircraft structures [2-5].

Fig. 1. Structure of fibre metal laminates (FMLs).

Aircraft industry had been using monolithic aluminium for manufacturing of fuselage for a long time, but due to its high density and low strength to weight ratio, the need for better and lighter materials arose [6]. In 1950s, the Dutch Fokker aircraft company chose to adapt to laminated bonded structures mainly for cost effectiveness leading to the first introduction of fibre metal laminates in aircraft components [7]. During this period, the key advantage of FML was identified as its ability to prevent fatigue crack growth through the thickness of the material. Having layers of prepreg covered by metal sheet provided shielding for prepreg against moisture, whereas a layer of prepreg prevented fatigue crack propagation through to the inner layer of metal. Subsequent fatigue tests showed that aircraft components made of FMLs have a longer life cycle than those of conventional composite

materials [8]. Another favourable property of FMLs is their high strength to weight ratio; reducing weight to about 20-50% compared to a full aluminium structure. FMLs also have high fire damage tolerance and lower cost compared to aluminium sheets [7]. These properties made FMLs very attractive for aircraft engineering.

Typically, carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy are used as FRPs in FMLs, commercially available as ARALL (Aramid Reinforced ALuminium Laminate) [9, 5] and GLARE (GLASS REinforced) [9, 3], respectively. The use of these hybrid materials has increased over the past decade because of the acceptance of these materials by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and European Aviation Authorities, majorly due to the failure of aluminium developers to improve their products. Applications of FMLs were then extended to the fuselage skin of aircraft. In 1980s, a range of FMLs were developed with improved mechanical characteristics [7]. This was achieved by an optimised, carefully balanced mix of thin aluminium layers combined with fibre/epoxy layers. First generation of FMLs, ARALL, were developed primarily for aircraft wing applications, as they proved to be significantly lighter than metal [5]. A significant weight saving of 20-30%, compared to monolithic aluminium, was achieved when ARALL was used to build full scale wing panels for Fokker-50 and Fokker-27 [6] aircraft during 1984-87. Despite this, ARALL had certain disadvantages, such as limitation of fibre volume fractions, poor compression and the inherent anisotropic properties of the laminate [10], that limited its extensive use for fuselage.

Later, a stiffer variant of ARALL which consisted of carbon fibres instead of aramid fibres, the CARALL laminates, were developed [11]. Recent research has shown that CARALL laminates also suffered from fibre failures occurring during flight-simulation fatigue tests at elevated stress levels, which resulted in poor fatigue performance. Limited failure strain of carbon fibres (0.5–2.0%) was thought to be a disadvantage [3] due to its sensitivity to notch behaviour compared to monolithic aluminium alloy. Galvanic corrosion between carbon fibres and aluminium sheet in moisture environment also presented difficulties.

Second generation of FMLs, GLARE, was introduced in 1987 [12, 9]. In contrast to ARALL,

that had unidirectional fibre layers, GLARE was optimised to have both unidirectional and cross-ply variants [5]. The introduction of glass fibre reinforcement improved the fibre-matrix adhesion compared to that for aramid or carbon fibres. Moreover, glass fibres are much more resistant to compressive loading, thus reducing the possibility of fibre failure during fatigue loading. Glass fibres in FML were meant to provide not only higher compressive strength, but also thermal insulation. In 1988-89, full scale A330/340 fuselage manufacturing was achieved using GLARE as the core material [3]. GLARE provides several superior properties, out of which the impact characteristics make them an excellent material for impact sensitive areas, such as the cockpit crown, forward bulkheads, and leading edge.

However, the acceptance of such hybrid materials depends on both the cost balance throughout the life of aircraft and the development of new fabrication techniques to make the optimum use of material properties. Due to complexity of manufacturing and repair difficulties, considerable research in the past several years has focused on developing proper material combinations, processing and manufacturing methods. One of the major issues was the prolonged processing cycle required for complete curing of the thermoset matrix and optimised bonding throughout the interlayer of the laminates due to the use of epoxy resin as matrix in early FMLs. In 2000, Reyes and Cantwell [1] produced FMLs using thermoplastic matrix instead of thermosets, which can significantly reduce processing time because the thermoplastic-based composites can be easily moulded and bonded to a metal substrate.

One limitation of FMLs is that they often have low impact resistance compared to pure metal sheets. Hence novel designs and manufacturing processes are continually explored to improve the impact resistance of FMLs [2]. The present work addresses this effort by developing and characterising the failure and impact behaviour of a specific type of FML, which utilises thermoplastic elastomers (TPE) instead of thermosets or thermoplastic polymers (TPP) with the aim to improve impact energy absorption capabilities. Impact response of the FMLs was characterised using low velocity impact tests as per standard

ISO6603 and modelled using the finite element method (FEM).

2. Materials

In this study aluminium sheets, thermoplastic elastomer (Santoprene™), adhesive (Fusabond™), glass fibre thermoplastic twill fabrics (Twintex®) and unidirectional FRP tapes (Plytron) were used for manufacturing FMLs with various layup configurations for performance characterisation, as listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Constituent materials used for FML manufacturing

Material	t mm	Mass g	ρ kg/m ³	E GPa	UTS MPa	Poisson's Ratio ν
Al-5052	0.6	250	2680	7.03	265	0.33
Al-5005	0.45	189.5	2700	6.89	180	0.33
Plytron	0.23	119.5	3413	17.50	338	0.40
Twintex	0.35	113.3	324	15.30	360	0.40
E-glass (Plain-weave)	0.35	120	943	70.00	3400	0.40
Santoprene (TPE)	-	158.6	970	0.0023	7	0.40

This study concerns with thermoplastic elastomer based FMLs and their performance is compared with thermoplastic polymer based FMLs. Two different aluminium alloys, Al-5052 and Al-5005, were used for two different layup configurations. One (Al-5005) was 0.45 mm thick for 3/2 layup, and the other one (Al-5052) was 0.6 mm thick for 2/1 layup. Plytron, a prepreg with unidirectional glass fibres reinforced in polypropylene (PP) matrix, was selected as one of the composites due to its noteworthy mechanical properties. Twintex, also a PP base glass fibre composite, was chosen as it comes in a fabric form with bi-weave arrangement.

Santoprene™, a thermoplastic elastomer with PP base from Monsanto, and a bonding adhesive (Fusabond™) was extruded from granular pellets into sheets which were then used to manufacture FRTPE laminates.

3. Manufacturing of FMLs

For successful manufacturing of the proposed elastomer based FML systems, each of the constituents needs to be properly prepared with standardised processing techniques to produce

materials in the useable form. The processing temperature window was identified using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) to ensure processability of the materials and the final product integrity.

The laminate manufacturing process is schematically shown in Fig. 2. The size of each sample was 395 × 395 mm. Four different combinations of FMLs were produced (Table 2) in two layup sequences, a 2/1 layup where there were 2 aluminium layers and 1 composite layer in the middle, and a 3/2 layup where there were 3 aluminium layers and 2 composite layers between them. The stacking sequence is described in Table 3.

Table 2: FML system combinations

1	Aluminium + Plytron
2	Aluminium + Twintex
3	Aluminium + Santoprene
4	Aluminium + Plain weave Glass fibre + Santoprene

Table 3: Stacking sequence and physical properties of manufactured FMLs

2/1 Layup - Al-5052 with FRP or FRE			
FRP/FRE used	Stacking Configuration	Thickness, mm	Mass, g
Plytron	Al/0-90 Plytron/Al	1.8	625
Twintex	Al/Twintex Bi-weave/Al	2.5	750.3
TPE	Al/TPE/E-Glass/TPE/Al	2.7	618.7

3/2 Layup - Al-5005 with FRP or FRE			
FRP/FRE used	Stacking Configuration	Thickness, mm	Mass, g
Plytron	Al/0-90 Plytron/Al/0-90 Plytron/Al	2.4	755.3
Twintex	Al/Twintex/Al/Twintex/Al	2.8	873.9
TPE	Al/TPE/E-Glass/TPE/Al/TPE/E-Glass/TPE/Al	5.2	1217.9

Fig. 2. Manufacturing process of FMLs.

Fig. 2 depicts the procedure of forming a typical 3/2 layup FML. Maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (MAPP), which was Fusabond™ P613 from DuPont™, was used as the adhesive interlayer for the thermoplastic polymer based FMLs. Several trials were carried out to determine the exact amount (90 g) of Fusabond that would cover the specimen area. The weighted pellets were then placed on the top of a Teflon sheet and placed inside the pre-heated mould. The pellets were pressed for about 2 minutes at a pressure of 0.3 MPa and a temperature of 165 °C.

The laminates were then hotpressed in a compression mould using a 100-ton Hydraulic Press. Table 4 shows the stacking configurations and the temperature and pressure profiles for different types of FMLs. Before stacking with their polymer composite counterparts, the aluminium sheets were dipped into 5% sodium hydroxide (caustic soda) solution whereby the aluminium was etched and its anodised layer was removed. The aluminium sheets were then air-dried. The surface roughness of the aluminium after etching promotes improved adhesion. The adhesive layers were then placed between the composite layer and aluminium sheet.

The mould was pre-heated to the desired forming temperature. The layers of laminates were placed inside the mould and pressure was applied to compress the layers together. A Teflon sheet, about 0.45 mm thickness, was used to prevent the laminates from sticking to the die. The material was held inside the mould for about 8 to 10 minutes for TPP based FMLs and 10 to 12 minutes for TPE based FMLs. To avoid residual stresses and delamination, the material was cooled to room temperature inside the mould.

Table 4: Stacking configurations and forming temperature and pressure of FMLs

Lay up	Configuration	Forming Temperature, °C	Forming Pressure, MPa	Hold Time, min
2/1	Al5052/0-90 Plytron/Al5052	185	0.5	8 - 10
2/1	Al5052/Twintex/Al5052	185	0.5	8 - 10
2/1	Al5052/TPE/E-Glass/TPE/Al5052	210	0.75	10-12
3/2	Al5005/0-90 Plytron/Al5005/0-90 Plytron/Al5005	185	0.5	8 - 10
3/2	Al5005/Twintex/Al5005/Twintex/Al5005	185	0.5	8 - 10
3/2	Al5005/TPE/E-Glass/TPE/Al5005/TPE/E-Glass/TPE/Al5005	210	0.75	10-12

As shown in Table 4, TPE layered FMLs (FRTPE) were compressed on a higher pressure and held inside the mould for a longer time to allow the molten TPE to fully permeate in between the fibres. This will ensure that the fibres will effectively act as reinforcement within the TPE matrix. In total, six different types of FML panels were manufactured, and tested for tensile and impact properties.

4. Test Methods

Failure behaviour of FML composites was studied experimentally using tensile and low speed impact tests.

4.1 Tensile Test Procedure

Tensile testing was performed according to ASTM D3039 to determine the tensile strength and modulus (Young's modulus) of the material. The test was conducted on an Instron 1185 universal testing instrument with a 50 mm gauge length and a 5 mm/min crosshead speed. Five parallel strip specimens (200 × 20 mm) were cut from each manufactured laminates with the cutting path parallel to the rolling direction of the aluminium. The test was instrumented so that the testing would terminate when the maximum stress drops by 40%. The first ply failure (FPF) stress levels were recorded and the failure mechanisms were observed. The force and extension data were recorded for further analysis of tensile properties.

4.2 Impact Test Procedure

Impact tests were conducted according to standard ISO 6603. The aim of the impact tests was to determine the amount of energy required to completely puncture the different types of FMLs. IM10T-20 impact tester from IMATEK was used for the tests. The equipment offers an ability to drop a weight from up to a height of 2 m at a velocity ranging from 1 to 6.26 m/s. The indenter used during the test had a hemispherical nose tip with a diameter of 20 mm and a weight of 1.133 kg. The total weight of the indenter assembly was 9.657 kg. Specimens measuring 100 × 100 mm were clamped into a circular frame with 40 mm inner and 60 mm outer diameter. Five samples for each type of FML were tested. The impact test was set so that the impactor assembly would drop from a certain height and generate impact energy of up to ~95J. The peak energy levels were measured. Reaction forces at the indenter and the specimen were recorded to draw its relationship with possible failure modes in the laminates.

5. Modelling

A finite element (FE) model was developed using ABAQUS to understand the impact response of the proposed FML system. The FE model consisted of two main parts, the FML specimen and the indenter. Fig. 3 shows the model setup and the plate and indenter geometries.

The specimens were modelled using composite shell elements, and composite layup was implemented to replicate each layer of the laminate. An annular partition was created with 40 mm inner and 60 mm outer diameters to replicate the clamps which held the specimen rigidly. The indenter was modelled as a rigid body with a mass of 9.657 Kg. The translational motions of the indenter were constrained in all directions except along the axial direction, shown by the dotted line, Fig. 3a. It was constrained to have a constant acceleration of 9.81 m/s² under gravity without any angular acceleration or rotational motion. The region of the plate highlighted by the annular section, Fig. 3a, was kept fixed throughout.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3. (a) Impact model setup, (b) Specimen with circular partition, and (c) Indenter with hemispherical nose tip.

In this study, a drop test was simulated to identify peak energy absorption. Tests were modelled at 25, 30, 35 and 40 J of impact energy to observe the failure of laminates and energy absorption.

Composite layup was created as shown in Fig. 4. The composite layup consisted of 16 layers with a symmetrical arrangement through centre ply. 8 layers were of Aluminium and remaining 8 were FRP/FRE placed in 0° and 90° orientation in global coordinates. Each layer had a constant thickness of 0.125 mm providing an overall thickness of 2 mm.

Fig. 4. Composite layup arrangement.

6. Results and Discussion

6.1 Modelling Results

The reaction forces experienced by the specimen and the indenter were determined from the simulations, and compared against the reaction force data from the impact tests.

A typical comparison of the reaction force on Plytron laminates for both 2/1 and 3/2 layups is shown in Fig. 5 for various impact energies. From the experimental results, it is observed that the peak reaction force for the 2/1 layup composites is consistently greater than that of the 3/2 layup composites. The finite element modelling predictions match reasonably well with the test results, given that the primary purpose of FE modelling was to predict the reaction forces at the initial stage of impact. Damage and fracture under post-impact complex deformation modes will be addressed in the future work using suitable continuum damage models.

Fig. 5. Peak force comparison for Plytron laminates

6.2 Tensile Test Results

Fig. 6 shows the fractured tensile samples of FMLs. Three different failure modes were observed: a) Localised grip failure was observed mainly in 3/2 FRE based laminates, Fig. 6a. This was due to the difference in elastic moduli of the FRE and aluminium layers of the composites. The resulting high force at the grips from the pinching of the jaws and non-uniform load sharing between the aluminium and FRE layers caused the samples to fail under in-plane shear and/or delamination between the metal and elastomeric layers, leading to subsequent failure of the outer aluminium layer.

(a) Grip failure - typical for most 3/2 layups especially for FRE based FMLs

(b) Fibre-reinforcement failure – typical for FRP based FMLs

(c) Delamination – typical for 3/2 FMLs

Fig. 6. Tensile failures of FML specimens

Failures due to reinforcement tensile fracture (Fig. 6b) and delamination (Fig. 6c) were considered to be the expected modes of failures, as this meant that the FML behaved in a more integral manner so that the load was shared between the metal and the FRE/FRP layers. The elongation of the FRE/FRP layer was restrained by the aluminium alloy, creating shear stresses along the interfaces. Continued elongation caused simultaneous fracture of the FRE/FRP and aluminium alloy and/or delamination of the plies. FRE based FMLs with 2/1 layups suffered tensile failures within the gauge length. The fibre reinforced layer was found intact whereas the aluminium alloy skin was extended beyond its maximum strain. So the key modes of failure were fracture and delamination both in the fibre reinforcement and aluminium skin.

The ultimate tensile strength and Young’s modulus of the different laminates were calculated

from the elongation and force data recorded and given in Table 5.

Table 5: Ultimate tensile strength and Young’s modulus of various FML laminates

Average Tensile Properties		
FML Type	E, GPa	σ_{UTS} , MPa
Twintex 1/2	37.08	206
Twintex 2/3	27.74	177
Plytron 1/2	51.31	163
Plytron 2/3	32.09	111
FRTPE 1/2	32.39	119
FRTPE 2/3	13.75	44

6.3 Impact Test Results

The results of the drop test at different energy levels were used to assess the failure and energy absorption characteristics for various FML configurations. From the drop test, peak energy for each type of laminate was determined. According to the peak energy, different energy profiles were set for each FML laminate.

Table 6 shows the energy profiles used for different types of FML laminates. The peak energy shown in Table 6 is the threshold (minimum) energy at which a specimen is penetrated by the indenter during impact.

Table 6: Drop test results and energy profiles for the FML laminates

Laminate configuration	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
	Santoprene 3/2	Twintex 3/2	Santoprene + Fibreglass 3/2	Santoprene 2/1	Twintex 2/1	Plytron 2/1	Plytron 3/2	Santoprene + Glass Fibre 2/1
Peak Energy (J)	22.67	28.38	36.47	30.06	26.92	27.35	18.14	36.57
Specimen 1	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Specimen 2	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Specimen 3	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
Specimen 4	30	40	40	40	40	40	20	40

Specimen 5	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
------------	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----

Fig. 7 shows the peak energy absorbed by the specimens at the penetration condition for various FML configurations. The fibre reinforced thermoplastic elastomer (FRTPE) based FMLs, represented by configurations C and I, were able to absorb the maximum amount of energy before complete failure. These configurations were manufactured using the combination of Santoprene and plain weave glass fibre, with a 3/2 layup for configuration C and 2/1 layup for configuration I.

Comparing the 3/2 layup FMLs (Fig. 7 - blue shade bars), configuration C performed significantly better than the rest with respect to impact energy absorption. Configuration B (Twintex 3/2 layup) had the second highest energy absorption with its peak energy being 22% lower than that of configuration C. Configurations A (Santoprene 3/2) and H (Plytron 3/2) had 37% and 50% lower peak energies, respectively, compared to that of configuration C.

In the 2/1 layup category (Fig. 7 – red shade bars), configuration I (Santoprene and glass fibre) performed significantly better as expected with the highest peak energy absorption. Configuration D was the second best with 17% less energy absorption than that of configuration I. Configurations F and E absorbed 25% and 26% lower energy, respectively, compared to that of configuration I.

Fig. 7. Peak energy absorption of various FML configurations for the drop test.

Variation of force on the specimen during impact was monitored so that it could be correlated with the failure pattern. Fig. 8 shows the failure initiation in the different FML laminates tested (Table 6). A smooth curve such as the red one for configuration C indicates that failure/damage of the

specimen had not been initiated under the given (in this case 40 J) impact energy, and so the specimen absorbed all of the energy impacted. The curves with oscillations indicate that failure/damage had started for the corresponding specimens under the given impact energy. This shows that FRTPE based FMLs are effective in preventing penetration/puncture type failures, although they can deform considerably due to low stiffness.

Fig. 8. Failure initiation for various FML configurations indicated by the force profile.

The force profiles of the fibre reinforced thermoplastic elastomers (FRTPE) (i.e. Santoprene and Glass fibre) at different impact energies for both 3/2 (C) and 2/1 (I) layups are shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, respectively. For configuration C, the impact test data shows that the maximum force reached in the specimen before failure was approximately 8.9 kN at the highest energy level (95 J at 1 m drop height), as indicated by the light blue curve with small-scale force fluctuations, Fig. 9. The smooth curves for the other energy levels indicate that the specimens were able to withstand all of the impact energies without failure. The maximum force (at 40 J energy level) for the corresponding 2/1 layup FRTPE (Fig. 10) was somewhat lower, being approximately 8.1 kN.

IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF ELASTOMER BASED FIBRE METAL LAMINATES

Fig. 9. Force profile of FRTPE (Santoprene + Glass fibre) based FML with 3/2 layup (configuration C).

Fig. 10. Force profile of FRTPE (Santoprene + Glass fibre) based FML with 2/1 layup (configuration I).

(a) 3/2 laminate layups for Plytron, Twintex and FRTPE FMLs (left to right)

(b) 2/1 laminate layups for Plytron, Twintex and FRTPE FMLs (left to right)
 Fig. 11. Failure patterns of perforated FML laminates: Plytron, Twintex and FRTPE.

The perforation threshold energies for various laminates are provided in Table 7. It was found that the FRTPE laminates have the highest perforation threshold energy. Impact velocity change was also measured to determine the kinetic energy loss of the indenter caused due to energy absorption by the composite material. It is to be noted that the 3/2 FRTPE laminate completely stopped the indenter. This shows that the FRTPE laminates have high impact energy absorption ability compared to conventional thermoplastic laminates.

Table 7: Perforation/puncture energy of the FML configurations according to ISO 6603 impact test.

FML Type	Puncture Energy, J	Velocity Change, %
Twintex 2/1	26.92	60
Twintex 3/2	28.38	57.21
Plytron 2/1	27.35	30.74
Plytron 3/2	18.14	27.26
FRTPE 2/1	36.57	62.36
FRTPE 3/2	36.47	109.34

The perforated FML laminates after the impact testing are shown in Fig. 11. It was found that the FRTPE 3/2 laminates showed improved resistance to impact perforation. The key difference between the perforation mechanisms between the elastomeric and non-elastomeric laminates is that the elastomeric

FRTPE laminates suffered severe in-plane stretching and out-of-plane localised deformation around the perforated hole. This contributed to the absorption of significant impact energy. In contrast, for the other thermoplastic based (Plytron and Twintex) FMLs, a relatively sharp, completely punctured hole (about 20 mm diameter) was created, demonstrating that the material did not undergo sufficient local deformation, and hence was not as effective in absorbing part of the impact energy.

Fig. 12. Fibre ruptures during impact and perforation in the FMLs

Fibre-matrix rupture (Fig. 12) occurred implying that the fibre-reinforcement decelerated the indenter and the matrix largely absorbed its kinetic energy. Extensive delamination was observed as the fibres were pulled towards the centre of the impact

indentation zone. Crack propagation at the rear end of the specimens was also noted.

7. Summary

A relatively novel thermoplastic elastomer based fibre metal laminate has been successfully manufactured in this study. The FMLs manufactured were mechanically tested to investigate its tensile and impact behaviour.

The tensile test results showed that FRTPE laminates are weaker in strength and stiffness compared to conventional thermoplastic FMLs, primarily due to the presence of elastomer. However, they provide enhanced impact resistance in terms of energy and shock absorptions. As most of the panels were failing at the grips, a different testing method to investigate tensile properties of such panels is recommended.

The impact testing showed that 3/2 laminates have the ability to absorb significant impact energy without puncturing. This may be of interest to current aircraft industry where hail storms and bird strikes are common in routine in-service operations. In conclusion, this study has provided with promising results in terms of energy absorption of FMLs when thermoplastic elastomer based layers are introduced. However, the perpetual delamination of the laminates needs further investigations to determine an optimal method to improve the plastic/metal interfacial bonding.

Acknowledgements

Authors would like to thank undergraduate students Mr Rhys Gargason and Mr Mikeshe Patel for their assistance in experiments and testing.

References

- [1] G. Reyes V, and W.J. Cantwell "The mechanical properties of fibre-metal laminates based on glass fibre reinforced polypropylene". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 60, No. 7, pp 1085-1094, 2000.
- [2] A. Vlot "Impact loading on fibre metal laminates". *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, Vol. 18, No. 3, pp 291-307, 1996.
- [3] A. Asundi, and A.Y.N. Choi "Fiber metal laminates: an advanced material for future aircraft". *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, Vol. 63, No. 1-3, pp 384-394, 1997.
- [4] R. Abbott, 2000. 6.09 - Composites in General Aviation. In *Comprehensive Composite Materials*, ed. K. Editors-in-Chief: Anthony and Z. Carl, pp. 165-180, Oxford: Pergamon.
- [5] L.B. Voegesang, and A. Vlot "Development of fibre metal laminates for advanced aerospace structures". *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, Vol. 103, No. 1, pp 1-5, 2000.
- [6] L.B. Voegesang, and J.W. Gunnink "ARALL: A materials challenge for the next generation of aircraft". *Materials and Design*, Vol. 7, No. 6, pp 287-300, 1986.
- [7] J. Schijve "Fatigue of aircraft materials and structures". *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp 21-32, 1994.
- [8] J.W. Gunnink "Damage tolerance and supportability aspects of ARALL laminate aircraft structures". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp 83-104, 1988.
- [9] Development of fibre-metal laminates, ARALL and GLARE, new fatigue resistant materials. J. Schijve, 1993. *Delft University of Technology*, Delft. Report No. LR-715.
- [10] R. Van Rooijen, J. Sinke, T.J. De Vries, and S. Van Der Zwaag "Property Optimisation in Fibre Metal Laminates". *Applied Composite Materials*, Vol. 11, No. 2, pp 63-76, 2004.
- [11] R.C. Alderliesten, and S. J "Delamination growth rate at low and elevated temperatures in glare.". In: *25th international congress of the aeronautical sciences*, Vol. No. 2006 September 3-8, pp 1-7, 2006.
- [12] G. Roebroeks 1991. Towards GLARE - The development of a fatigue insensitive and damage tolerant aircraft material. Doctoral Thesis, Delft University of Technology.